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Supervisory And Talent Management Practices As Indicators Of Teacher Productivity In Public Senior Secondary Schools In Rivers State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

This examined the relationship between Principals' supervisory and talent management practices as indicators of teacher productivity in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study was guided by two objectives with corresponding research questions and null hypotheses. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of this study consisted of all three hundred and eleven (311) public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. 380 teachers are representing all of the schools. They were selected using purposive and stratified random sampling techniques. The instruments titled: 'Principals' Supervisory and Talent Management Practices Assessment Scale' and 'Teacher Productivity Assessment Scale' were adopted. The questionnaire was validated by the researchers' supervisors and one other expert in Measurement and Evaluation at, University of Port Harcourt. Research questions were analyzed using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Formula (r). The z ratio was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. The results of the findings revealed that the productivity of teachers' jobs is significantly enhanced when principals implement supervisory and talent management practices for teaching staff. These practices include providing effective supervision and feedback to ensure the quality of instruction and implementing talent management strategies to identify and nurture teachers' specific strengths. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Secondary school principals should implement proactive talent management strategies aimed at identifying, nurturing, and retaining the diverse talents of their teaching staff. These practices should be designed to optimize teachers' job satisfaction and performance, ultimately leading to increased overall productivity and student success.

Keywords: Principals, supervisory practices, talent management practices, teacher productivity, Rivers State.

INTRODUCTION

The school serves as a key platform for implementing and delivering established educational policies. As an organization, its primary task is to shape students into responsible and effective adults. To achieve educational goals, it is essential that teachers are well-prepared, motivated, and capable of delivering high-quality education. The ultimate objective of educational administration at all levels is to develop an inclusive and quality education that is accessible and relevant, promoting self-reliance. Good education plays a significant role in economic growth and improves employment prospects, creating income-generating opportunities that support sustainable development. To achieve quality education, teachers

(human resources) and financial and instructional facilities (material resources) must be properly organized. This means that secondary school teachers must be well-trained and supervised, learners must be continuously evaluated, and adequate funding and resources must be provided.

Secondary school principals act as custodians of public secondary institutions. They are responsible for implementing all programs developed under the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013). Their roles are similar to those in other educational institutions, including interpreting policies, executing curriculum programs, ensuring the welfare of students and staff, maintaining equipment and facilities, training staff, and fostering effective relationships within the school community. Proper record management, communication, and decision-making processes are also essential for school principals to promote commitment and effectiveness. No principal can achieve educational goals without the support of their staff. To ensure success, a clear framework should be established within the school, assigning roles based on merit and expertise for specific duties. Strategic implementation allows principals to delegate tasks to academic and non-academic staff according to their competencies, minimizing conflicts since everyone understands their responsibilities. Effective organization enables the principal to coordinate various aspects of the school, enhancing overall functionality. Teaching has become increasingly complex, requiring high operational standards. As a vital profession, it significantly impacts the effectiveness of other fields. Teachers are key agents of change in today's knowledge-driven society, playing a crucial role in the dissemination of knowledge. Without competent teachers, the future of the school system and the quality of education would be at risk. This underscores the essential role teachers play in promoting effective and functional education. They have a profound and lasting influence on their students, directly affecting how much they learn and what they learn, as well as how they interact with each other and the world around them.

According to Okekeuche (2020), secondary school principals are saddled with the responsibility to relate the necessary information required of a teacher to perform their job effectively. Okekeuche further states that, where teachers are assimilated and it appears to have some discrepancies in their knowledge of the organization, it means that assimilation toward such organization is lagging. In the same vein, teachers who are properly assimilated and integrated into the teaching profession from their first days of getting into the system will exhibit high and better morals and confidence in their assigned areas of subjects and other functions.

Proper staff assimilation practice is the surest, strongest, and fastest wheel of movement in the achievement of the expected productivity in any organizational set-up.

Principal as an Administrator and Strategist

The principal is the administrative head of the secondary school in-charge of managing the activities and programmes as well as the available resources for productivity and quality outputs. Secondary school principals must manage the resources available in the school such as the human, material, financial, energy, and time resources for improved teachers' job performance. The principal as the leader of the secondary school is responsible for supervision and other administrative tasks to improve teachers' job effectiveness (Nwabueze, 2016). The principal provides good leadership, proper direction, and effective coordination within the school to develop and maintain effective educational programmes and promote the improvement of teaching and learning in the school. The principals have the responsibilities for the detailed organization of the school, development of the instructional programme, assignment of duties to members of his staff, the general operation of the school facilities, and whole school supervision (Wallace Foundation, 2013). In Nigeria, principals are the appointed executive heads or administrative heads of secondary schools (Ogbonnaya, 2004). The principals are the agents and government representatives of the Ministry of Education charged with the responsibilities of administration to ensure the achievement of effective teaching and learning needed for the realization of the goals of education at the level.

The principal as a supervisor assesses and records the performance of teachers, their ability, and consistency in carrying out classroom activities. The activities of the principal as the supervisor include: inspecting, monitoring, rating, assisting, recommending, etc. All these activities if carried out

professionally will aim at improving teachers' productivity in instructional delivery. Teachers' efficiency reflects on the interactive skills and knowledge adopted in the process of teaching and learning. Efficient teachers know what to teach and how to teach as they have very wide teaching skills and the ability to use them promptly (Shechtman & Leichtenritt, 2004). Teachers' efficiency equally generates good attitudes and behaviour that ease learning difficulties among the students. In other words, teachers who have the creative ability always enable the students to work effectively and proactively through adequate supervision. This has equally necessitated the involvement of school principals in the supervision of the teachers for the achievement of the expected outcomes. Principals' supervision in the modern era centres on the improvement of the teaching-learning situation to the benefit of both the teachers and learners. This is because it helps in the identification of areas of strengths and weaknesses of teachers. This implies a follow-up activity that is equally directed at the improvement of identified areas of teachers' weaknesses thus creating a cordial working atmosphere based on good human relations. Common experiences revealed that principals' supervision constitutes the leverage point for instructional improvement, teacher's competence and efficiency of the educational system while unsupervised instruction may mar the standard of education. Thus, principals as catalysts facilitate the implementation of the various sets of instructional activities geared towards an effective, viable, vibrant and qualitative educational system that will improve the teaching-learning situation. As expressed by this scholar, it is directed towards sustaining and ameliorating the teaching-learning process in the educational system, as education plays an essential role in the growth and development of any nation socially, politically and economically. Supervision by the principals implies directing, overseeing, guiding or to make sure that expected standards are met. This reflects on the principles, rules, regulations and methods prescribed to implement and achieve the objectives of education. The principals therefore use expert knowledge and experiences to oversee, evaluate and coordinate the process of improving teaching and learning activities in schools. As Nwakpa (2014) reveal the targets of supervision are: - To make sure that minimum standards are adhered to. The intention of this is to provide a relatively equal educational opportunity for all children by ensuring that set school standards are maintained. - To provide a forum through which purposeful and constructive advice can be rendered for the sake of improving the quality of teaching in school through the improvement of educational facilities. - To make sure that prudence is maintained in the way and manner that public funds are spent in running the schools. - To make available to the appropriate authorities the true position of human and material resources as they concern the schools through reports. Some of the issues under review here include: availability of space, size of classes, state of facilities, staff strength and appropriateness of teaching qualification of teachers as well as the perceptions of the other numerous difficulties that the school has to contend with. To stimulate and guide the display of desirable education practices while noting the various negative education practices. excessive turnover is capturing the attention of education research and development. The main goal of educationalists is to know about the reasons for excessive teacher turnover. This problem is not only prevailing in Bahawalpur but also the same situation is prevailing in the other cities of Pakistan as well as in other countries. Secondary school teachers become demotivated due to low salaries and poor facilities like lack of developmental programmes. In other words, teachers' productivity increases when satisfactory feedback is provided in the process or during the period of exercising their responsibilities. Edo (2016) lends support to the above standpoint that feedback plays a fundamental role in the motivation of teachers. Likewise, these scholars have also researched teachers' productivity and concluded the same result that feedback plays an imperative role in improving the morale of teachers. Some other researchers, who conducted their research on employee motivation, especially on teacher motivation, conclude that appraisal contributes much to teachers' productivity. Appraisals have an enormous impact on the productivity of teachers in the long run. This implies that appraisals play an important role in modifying teacher's behaviour about work activities. Thus, for the enhancement of teachers' capacity, the environment and facilities available have a vital contribution to academic pursuit. In other words, when

the principals create an environment that is friendly and pleasurable, the extent of academic achievement will be much more viable.

Another important practice that may be employed by the principals to enhance the job performance of teachers is the adequate provision of instructional facilities to improve teachers' job performance in schools. Adeyemi (2011) states that providing teachers with the required working tools or facilities is one of the surest ways of enhancing their job performance. Cheng and Tui (2012) also observe that teacher job performance and effectiveness in curriculum implementation rest on adequate motivation and availability of instructional materials in schools. Bass (2009) equally observes that, when principals provide teachers with adequate teaching facilities, they are not only happy with the performance of their duties but are made to improve their performance functions for increased productivity in the school system. For any organization to achieve predetermined goals, there must be effective and efficient administration whose responsibility is to plan, organize, coordinate, control, budget and report the effort to others. The practice of administration is as old as humanity, and keen attention should be given to it if success will be recorded thereafter. It is the art and science of a formal systematic plan process and careful arrangement of an institution for the achievement of its objectives. Administration is a social process concerned with identifying, maintaining, motivating, controlling and unifying formally and informally organized human and material resources within an integrated system designed specifically to achieve predetermined objectives. Administration has to do with getting things done with the accomplishment of defined objectives.

Teacher Job Productivity

Teacher productivity is a measure of how efficiently the teaching and learning process utilizes its workforce, which significantly impacts student outcomes. It refers to the extent of output generated from a specific task, such as teaching, relative to the input of the teacher. Essentially, it reflects the level of responsibility a teacher can manage within a given timeframe. The success of any school in achieving its goals largely depends on the efficiency and effectiveness of its teachers. According to Ajayi and Afolabi (2012), teacher productivity is evident in principals' evaluations, student assessments of their teachers, and students' academic performance. Teacher job productivity encompasses all the efforts and activities teachers engage in within schools while balancing the many demands of their profession and focusing on student learning and growth. This productivity requires ongoing effort, self-awareness, and a commitment to continuous improvement. Ebireri (2015) further emphasizes the critical importance of teacher productivity, which has led to calls for thorough supervision by school-based leaders, typically principals. This supervision aims to encourage teachers to uphold high professional and ethical standards, enabling them to adapt effectively to the evolving landscape of 21st-century education. The ultimate goal is to enhance teacher productivity and ensure they are well-equipped to navigate the dynamic educational environment.

Teacher productivity is crucial for effective teaching and positive educational outcomes. Productive teachers tend to achieve better results in student learning, classroom management, and overall job satisfaction (Abdikadir, 2018). A teacher is considered productive when they carry out their academic responsibilities with minimal errors, leading to improved student performance. Productivity is defined by the relationship between total input and total output of goods and services. Teacher productivity is also reflected in students' performance on internal and external examinations. Students taught by productive teachers typically demonstrate positive behaviour and performance, making meaningful contributions to school, family, and society. In summary, teacher productivity encompasses performance efficiency, effectiveness, quality, and commitment, all working together to achieve school goals.

Principals' Supervision Practice techniques and Teacher Productivity

The concept of supervision has various definitions based on different perspectives and contexts. There are two primary types of supervision: internal and external. External supervision involves officials from the State Ministry of Education and the Post-Primary Education Management Board visiting both public and private schools. Their purpose is to evaluate and determine the extent to which these schools comply with

state policies and standards regarding school operations. The functions of external supervisors are similar to those of inspectors, whose job is to check the adherence of school programs, teachers, and instructional facilities to established standards (Abraham, 2013). In contrast, internal supervision occurs within the school environment and is conducted by the school leadership. This type of supervision is primarily coordinated and executed by the principal, department heads, or experienced educators designated by the principal.

Supervision is a vital tool for the effective functioning of any organization, including the school system, and should be taken seriously. It involves a relationship between two individuals: the supervisor and the supervisee. The supervisor may be the school principal or an external party, while the supervisee is typically the teacher. The aim of supervision is to enhance the quality and standards of teaching, as teachers interact directly with students. Consequently, effective supervision also seeks to maximize student performance. Adequate supervision is essential for improving quality control within our educational system today. With globalization, education has shifted from being teacher-centered to child-centered. Therefore, to enhance educational standards and ensure quality productivity, effective school supervision must be implemented. The primary objective of learning is to facilitate transformational changes in students' behavior, influenced by the quality of instruction they receive. For this transformation to occur, the quality of teaching must be prioritized. Thus, supervision should focus on enhancing teacher quality, ensuring compliance with instructional materials, and evaluating student performance in continuous assessments and promotion examinations. Achieving the goals of education requires mechanisms such as supervision. Ogbo (2015) defines supervision as the process of developing an individual into their best self, capable of effectively carrying out teaching and learning tasks. School supervision aims to improve teachers' performance and encourage active student participation in the classroom. This indicates that supervision primarily seeks to cultivate positive attitudes and skills among teachers, enabling them to achieve excellence in their instruction.

Furthermore, supervision is not merely about enforcing rules and regulations; it is also about fostering good relationships, recognizing those who deserve it, and ensuring all parties involved in schoolwork feel supported, thereby facilitating learning. To achieve these aims, planning and professional development for teachers are crucial.

Principals Teaching Staff Talent Management and Teacher Productivity

Talent management centres on developing high-potential teachers that will foster the achievement of school goals. A teacher who has several skills is seen as a talented teacher, in other words, a teacher's talent is a teacher's possession of innate teaching abilities which will help one succeed in the classroom. Managing a teacher's talent is the act of supervising the teacher's talent such that the goals of a school are achieved. Managing teachers' talent is seen as a process of harnessing inborn skills in teachers to maximize productivity. Teachers' talents are also seen as those natural skills that distinguish a teacher from other teachers. Armstrong (2012) advocates that talent management is the process of making sure that schools have the right people needed to achieve desired goals. Therefore, he suggests that it is an important tool for school principals to manage the talents of their teachers to achieve educational goals.

The success of any school rests on the hands of their teachers' contribution and commitment, hence the importance of managing the talents of teachers. When the talent of teachers is highlighted and managed, they can be placed in the appropriate positions where their potentials are effectively utilized. As new teachers are recruited to teach students, there is a need for school principals to identify and develop these talents to maximize productivity, and to achieve the much-needed productivity, there is a need to manage the inherent talents of teachers.

Conclusively, Teachers don't only help students understand the lesson taught, but they also try to make their lesson meaningful to students. To be a talented teacher, one needs to focus on all the domains of teaching cognitive, affective and psychomotor. When teachers are talented and their talents properly managed by the school principals they tend to be useful and productive in nurturing the students. Teachers who are motivated are likely to go the extra mile to improve student performance and ensure

that the learning outcomes are achieved. Unfortunately, teachers in SSA countries, particularly those teaching in primary schools have been reported to have poor motivation and low job satisfaction (Wolf, Torrente, McCoy, & Rasheed, 2015). As the rate of student enrolment continues to increase in the region, the increased workload, overcrowding of classrooms, and the perceived relegation of teaching as an unappealing profession by society are potential issues that may lower teachers' motivation and job satisfaction. Additionally, constraints to boosting teachers' motivation may be in the form of poor remuneration, ineffective administrative supervision, low government support, lack of teaching incentives, absence of teaching materials, and poor teaching conditions (Jerotich & Box, 2015; UNESCO-IICBA, 2017). It was found that the higher the intrinsic motivation of teachers, the higher the degree of implementation of the innovative curriculum and teachers' positive attitudes towards it, as well as their intentions to implement it in the future (Gorozidis & Papaloannou, 2011). Larraz *et al.* (2017) analyzed the effects of cooperative learning; the results show the development of transferable skills, such as leadership skills, negotiation, reflection, teamwork, and improved social interactions. Therefore, cooperative learning can be considered a key instrument for the professionalization of Teachers and Principals in training programs.

Statement of the problem

Teacher productivity in Rivers State is a crucial topic, especially when we look at how well students perform academically and morally. New teachers should receive proper guidance when they start in a new school to improve their productivity. If school principals properly supervise newly hired teachers, it can help them adapt to their new jobs and environments more quickly and effectively. Therefore, it is essential to ensure that new teachers participate in necessary training programs, including supervision and talent management. Unfortunately, the current situation often shows the opposite. Many new teachers, who usually have little to no background in teaching, are allowed to enter the profession without proper support. At the same time, some school principals show little interest in what these teachers can offer. Instead, we see principals who are relaxed and consider it a waste of time and resources for new teachers to undergo training. Some even misuse funds meant for these programs and do not see them as important. On the other hand, there are principals who actively try to guide new teachers, but often the teachers do not take these programs seriously. This lack of engagement contributes to poor student performance. Given all this, I am concerned about whether proper supervision and talent management for new teachers can lead to better productivity.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

This study examined the relationship between Principals' supervisory and talent management practices as indicator of teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Specifically, the objectives were to:

1. examine the prediction of principals' teaching staff supervisory practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. establish the prediction of principals' teaching staff talent management practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

1. What is the prediction of principals' teaching staff supervisory practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What is the prediction of principals' teaching staff talent management practice on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant prediction of principals' teaching staff supervisory practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant prediction of principals' teaching staff talent management practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The correlational research design was used for this study. The population of this study consisted of all three hundred and eleven (311) public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The total sample size for the study was 380 teachers, which comprised both male and female. This sample size was arrived at after applying the Taro Yamane minimum sample size determination formula. These respondents were selected using purposive and stratified random sampling techniques. Two self-developed instruments were used as the medium through which data were obtained for this research. The instruments are titled: ‘Principals’ Supervisory and Talent Management Practices Assessment Scale’ (PSTMPAS), and ‘Teacher Productivity Assessment Scale’ (TPAS). The instruments used for this study were subjected to content and face validity. The validation was done by three experts, from the department of Educational Management, as well as from Measurement and Evaluation, under the Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling, who examined and made corrections on the instruments. The reliability of the two instruments were determined by the use of the Cronbach Alpha formula. Three hundred and eighty (380) copies of the instruments were administered by the researcher and two research assistants. Respondents were given 2 hours to respond to the instruments. On retrieval, 375 were retrieved, which represented 99 percent of the respondents. In the process of coding, 3 were discarded, leaving a total of 372. This 372 represent the 98 percent of the total number administered and 99 percent of the total number retrieved. Research questions were answered using Pearson’s Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, while z ratio was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level using SPSS version 27.0.1 analysis tool.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the prediction of principals’ teaching staff supervisory practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis (Ho₁): There is no significant prediction of principals’ teaching staff supervisory technique practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Showing the prediction of principals’ teaching staff supervisory technique practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Variables	N	df	R	P (Sig.)	Decision
Principals’ Teaching Staff Supervisory Practices	372	370	0.655	0.001	Rejected Ho ₅ (Significant)
Teacher Productivity	372				P < 0.05

Decision Rule: 0.00 – 0.25 = Very Weak, 0.26 – 0.50 = Weak, 0.51 – 0.75 = Strong, 0.71 – 1.00 = Very Strong

The results presented in Table 1 reveal a strong correlation coefficient (r=0.655) suggesting a strong prediction of principals' teaching staff supervisory practices on teachers productivity. Base on the finding, the research established that there is a strong prediction of principals' teaching staff supervisory practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The correlation coefficient of 0.655 is considered statistically significant with a probability value (p) of 0.001, which is lower than the critical value of 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating a significant prediction of principals' teaching staff supervisory practices on teacher productivity. Based on the above observation, the researcher established that there is a significant prediction of principals' teaching staff supervisory practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *What is the prediction of principals' teaching staff talent management practice on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Hypothesis (Ho₂): There is no significant prediction of principals' teaching staff talent management practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation Showing the prediction of principals' teaching staff talent management practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Variables	N	df	R	P (Sig.)	Decision
Principals' Teaching Staff Talent Management Practices Teacher Productivity	372	370	0.557	0.048	Rejected Ho ₆ (Significant) P < 0.05

Decision Rule: 0.00 – 0.25 = Very Weak, 0.26 – 0.50 = Weak, 0.51 – 0.75 = Strong, 0.71 – 1.00 = Very Strong

The data presented in Table 2 shows a strong correlation coefficient 'r', of 0.557. This indicates a strong prediction of principals' teaching staff talent management on teacher productivity. Base on the finding, the research established that there is a strong prediction of principals' teaching staff talent management on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

In addition, the results of the hypothesis test in Table 2 indicate that the correlation of 0.557 is statistically significant with a probability value (p-value) of 0.048, which is less than the critical value of 0.05. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis, suggesting a significant prediction of principals' teaching staff talent management on teacher productivity. Base on the above observation, the researcher established that there is a significant prediction of principals' teaching staff talent management on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Principals' Teaching Staff Supervisory Practices on Teacher Productivity

The first finding of the research established that there is a strong prediction of principals' teaching staff supervisory practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Additionally, the researcher established that there is a significant prediction of principals' teaching staff supervisory practices on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State. This result agreed with the perception of Edo (2016) who idealized that principals' supervision in the modern era centers on the improvement of the teaching-learning situation to the benefits of both the teachers and learners. This is because it helps in the identification of areas of strengths and weaknesses of teachers. This implies a follow-up activity that is equally directed at the improvement of identified areas of teachers' weaknesses thus create a cordial working atmosphere based on good human relations. Supporting this assertion Nwakpa (2014) affirmed that it provides an opportunity through which purposeful and constructive advice can be rendered for the sake of improving the quality of teaching in school through improvement of educational facilities. In other words, it provide a verifiable foundation upon which various courses of action can be initiated by the teachers and principal locally within the school, and the inspectors and government on a larger scale. The finding is in consonance with the view of Wiles in Adepoju (2014) which acknowledged that the primary aim of supervision is to monitor the implementation of curricular and ensure desirable increase in the teachers' capabilities, upgrade their conceptual knowledge and teaching skills, give them support in their work to facilitate better performance.

Principals' teaching staff talent management practice on teacher productivity

The second find of the research established that there is a strong prediction of principals' teaching staff talent management on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State. Also, the researcher established that there is a significant prediction of principals' teaching staff talent management on teacher productivity in public secondary schools in Rivers State. The finding is in agreement with Cheese (2008) who hinted that talent motivates the improvement in quality. Innovation and productivity therefore managing such talents is important so as to develop teachers especially the new teachers with regards to their work, behavior and social values because every teacher comes with different personality and perception. Also, in line with the finding Lockwood, (2006). Who asserted that when the talent of teachers is highlighted and managed, they can be placed in the appropriate positions where their potentials are effectively utilized. As new teachers are recruited to teach students, there is need for school principals to identify and develop these talents so as to maximize productivity, and in order to achieve the much needed for productivity, there is need to manage the inherent talents of teachers

CONCLUSION

Based on the research findings, it is concluded that the productivity of teachers is significantly enhanced when principals implement supervisory and talent management practices for teaching staff. These practices include It is evident that these multifaceted practices play a crucial role in nurturing and amplifying teachers' creative abilities within their respective subject areas when implemented with care and attention to individual needs.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Newly employed teachers should be attached to their senior colleagues who will mentor them on the academic activities of the school. The principals should make frantic efforts to monitor the development strategies and strands in each of the departments in the school in order to ensure that everyone is carried along and shown sense of belonging in their teaching profession.
2. School management should continue to prioritize organizing in-service training for teachers in order to enhance their proficiency in various teaching methods and their application for effective instructional delivery. Principals should urgently recognize the importance of exposing their teachers to training that enhances their proficiency in using teaching tools, ensuring they are not left behind in the ongoing advancements in educational practices.

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